

Drug induced recurrent hyponatremia: A case report

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ABSTRACT

This is a case report presenting a multifaceted medical condition of an elderly woman aged 63 years with a complex medical history which includes, trigeminal neuralgia, hypertension, hypothyroidism, coronary artery disease, and recurrent hyponatremia from medication. She was admitted with the history of a slip-and-fall accident with facial and head trauma, and during investigation, she was found to have severe hyponatremia with serum sodium level of 122 mmol/L. Recurrent hyponatremia in this patient was largely due to the use of carbamazepine & eslicarbazepine later ultrasound-guided drainage treated supplanting post eslicarbazepine treatment, both of which lead to SIADH. Even after her medication was modified and the electrolytic imbalance was managed with tolvaptan, the patient remained symptomatic with hyponatremia along with its complications such as syncope. The report aims at the issues arising from drug-induced hyponatremia in elderly patients with multiple prescriptions from different specialists and emphasizes the need for proactive serum electrolyte level monitoring. The case also helps to understand the need to educate about the side effects of medications and the critical role surgical intervention for chronic trigeminal neuralgia to minimize the need for recurrent offending anti-epileptic drugs.

Keywords: hyponatremia, Carbamazepine.

INTRODUCTION

Hyponatremia is defined as a condition in which sodium deficiency with plasma concentration below 135 mEq/L ⁽¹⁾, and the most common electrolyte disturbance among inpatients, responsible for 15-30% ^(2,3) of cases. While it is often mild and asymptomatic, hyponatremia deserves clinical attention because: a) it can rapidly lead to severe morbidity and mortality; b) it has a higher incidence of death and unfavourable outcome in hyponatraemic patients having a constellation of other illness; c) rapid correction of chronic hyponatremia endangers the patient to life-threatening damage of neurological structures. ⁽³⁾

PATHOGENESIS:

Hyponatremia is developed when an individual fails to remove excess water through the kidneys or when his/her intake of water exceeds body needs. Thus, thirst is induced by a rise of plasma osmolality and acts through hypothalamic osmoreceptors that

stimulate secretion of Anti diuretic hormone (ADH) from the posterior pituitary; ADH acts on V2 receptors of the kidney's collecting ducts, increasing aquaporin levels on the luminal side, facilitating water reabsorption and suppressing thirst. ⁽¹⁾ Hyponatremia may also be a result of the secretion of arginine vasopressin (AVP) under conditions of reduced effective circulating blood volume or by inappropriate, unmotivated release in the absence of any such stimuli. The antidiuretic action of AVP results in reduced urine output & vasopressin thereby causing hyponatremia. Clinical classification is usually performed in terms of total body sodium content, i.e., hypovolemic, euvolemic, or hypervolemic patients are differentiated from one another based on their volume ⁽²⁾

ETIOLOGY:

CATEGORIZED BASED ON VOLUME STATUS:

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1. Hypovolemic Hyponatremia:

Causes: Extrarenal sodium loss can occur due to prolonged vomiting, profuse diarrhoea, acute pancreatitis, excessive sweating, small bowel obstruction.

Renal sodium loss occurs due to osmotic diuresis, cerebral salt wasting, salt losing nephropathies, use of diuretics (especially thiazides), Addison's disease (primary adrenal insufficiency).

2. Euvolemic Hyponatremia:

Causes: Primary polydipsia, low solute intake (e.g., beer potomania, tea and toast diet), diuretic use (particularly in early stages), hypothyroidism, secondary adrenal insufficiency (cortisol deficiency), syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone secretion (SIADH) ^(2,3)

3. Hypervolemic Hyponatremia

Causes: Congestive heart failure, Hepatic cirrhosis, Nephrotic syndrome, very elderly chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients ⁽²⁾

CARBAMAZEPINE:

Carbamazepine is an anticonvulsant and analgesic agent primarily used to manage seizures and alleviate trigeminal neuralgia pain. First approved by the FDA in 1965, it is also employed in the stabilization of bipolar I disorder. Notably, carbamazepine holds the distinction of being the first anticonvulsant to be used in the treatment of bipolar disorder. ⁽⁴⁾

Carbamazepine is officially indicated for:

- Epilepsy, including mixed seizure types, partial seizures with complex features, and generalized tonic-clonic seizures. ^(4,5)
- Pain management specifically associated with classic trigeminal neuralgia. ⁽⁵⁾
- Bipolar I disorder, particularly in the treatment of acute manic episodes and mixed mania-depressive episodes. ⁽⁵⁾

Additionally, carbamazepine is frequently used off-label for several other conditions, including alcohol withdrawal syndrome and restless legs syndrome. ^(6,7)

Carbamazepine, though generally well tolerated among antiepileptic drugs, has a long-established profile of adverse effects such as:

- *Related to the mechanism of action of the drug:* Drowsiness, lethargy, tiredness, fatigue, dizziness, unsteadiness, diplopia, tremor; cognitive impairment; aggressive behaviour, depression; hyponatremia
- *Related to immunological or genetic susceptibility:* Drug reaction with eosinophilia and systemic symptoms, toxic epidermal necrolysis, Stevens Johnson syndrome, maculopapular exanthema; aplastic anaemia, agranulocytosis; hepatotoxicity, pancreatitis
- *Related to the cumulative dose:* Weight gain, bone disorders
- *Related to prenatal exposure to the drug (teratogenesis):* Congenital malformations such as neural tube defects, cardiovascular and urinary tract anomalies, and cleft palate. ⁽⁸⁾

Eslicarbazepine (ESL) is an oral antiepileptic agent in the class of dibenzazepines, related to oxcarbazepine and carbamazepine. It is used for the treatment of focal-onset seizures in adults. ESL inhibits the activity of voltage-gated sodium channels of the central nervous system by blocking them from opening. The drug is overall well tolerated with the most common side effects being dizziness, nausea, headache, and somnolence. Mild hyponatremia is a recognized side effect of ESL, though, such severe hyponatremia resulting in generalized tonic-clonic (GTC) seizures is uncommon. ⁽⁹⁾

Case report

A 63-year-old woman with a known history of trigeminal neuralgia, hypertension, hypothyroidism, coronary artery disease, dyslipidaemia, seizure disorder, and anaemia presented to the emergency department, after a slip and fall at home that resulted in head and cheek trauma, she remained fully conscious, with no vomiting or seizure activity. She was previously prescribed with carbamazepine (for trigeminal neuralgia), when the drug was suspected to

cause the hyponatremia, it was replaced with amitriptyline and gabapentin without any noticeable improvement. She was then prescribed with eslicarbazepine for pain control and levetiracetam for seizure control, and clonazepam was given PRN (pro re nata) for breakthrough seizures. Rosuvastatin, ezetimibe for the dyslipidaemia, later it was observed that she is resistant to statins and was then prescribed evolocumab, and started on atorvastatin and bempedoic acid for dyslipidaemia. Cilnidipine, bisoprolol and telmisartan were given to manage high blood pressure, tolvaptan was given to correct her hyponatremia. Over the past year, she had been admitted multiple times each time for different concerns, ranging from low sodium levels to episodes of facial pain, which would come and go and were usually managed with medication adjustments. This time she presented with complaints of slip & fall followed by sustained injury to head & right cheek, evaluated in other hospital, CT brain suggested of irregular hyperintensity in right ambient cistern (likely haemorrhage) with mild compression noted on the adjacent midbrain for which neurology opinion was also taken. ECG showed bradycardia with heart rate of **37 bpm** (normal 60–100 bpm), PR interval of **174 ms** (normal 120–200 ms), QRS duration of **84 ms** (normal <120 ms), QT interval of **353 ms** and corrected QT interval of **419 ms** (normal ≤470 ms in females), with a P-wave axis of **59°** (normal 0° to +75°), QRS axis of **-13°** (borderline leftward; normal -30° to +90°), and T-wave axis of **-8°** (normal +15° to +75°). Laboratory investigations revealed haemoglobin **10.4 g/dL** (normal 12–15.5 g/dL), haematocrit **31.9%** (normal 36–46%), RBC count **3.58 million/ μ L** (normal 3.9–5.0 million/ μ L), platelet count **3.10 lakhs/ μ L** (normal 1.5–4.5 lakhs/ μ L), blood urea **13 mg/dL** (normal 10–40 mg/dL), and serum creatinine **0.35 mg/dL** (normal 0.5–0.9 mg/dL). Biochemical profile showed total protein **6.6 g/dL** (normal 6.0–8.0 g/dL), **serum sodium 122 mmol/L** (severe hyponatremia; normal 135–145 mmol/L), serum chloride **88 mmol/L** (normal 98–106 mmol/L), serum potassium **4.7 mmol/L** (normal 3.5–5.0 mmol/L), and serum phosphate **1.5 mmol/L** (normal 0.8–1.5 mmol/L). Lipid profile showed total cholesterol **164 mg/dL** (normal <200 mg/dL), HDL **67 mg/dL** (desirable ≥50 mg/dL in women), LDL **84 mg/dL** (normal <100 mg/dL), and a total cholesterol/HDL ratio of **~2.4** (desirable <3.5).

Additional investigations revealed high-sensitivity CRP **5.46 mg/L** (elevated; normal <3 mg/L), lipoprotein (a) **52 mg/dL** (optimal <30 mg/dL), and vitamin D 25-OH was **26 ng/mL** (normal 30–100 ng/mL).

Based on the subjective and objective evidence the patient was diagnosed with **TRAUMATIC SUBARACHNOID HEMORRHAGE- RIGHT AMBIENT CISTERN & RECURRENT DRUG INDUCED SEVERE HYPONATREMIA.**

Patient had multiple admissions in the past to this hospital with various health conditions like pain and burning sensation of left half of face which increased in severity for 20 days when she was diagnosed with **LEFT TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA AND HTN.** Patient was asymptomatic until then. She was treated with carbamazepine 200mg TID PO, after 3 months of usage it was found to cause hyponatremia when she revisited the hospital with the complaints of high BP (197/110mmhg). She also had dyspnoea on exertion class 2, chest pain, burning micturition, dizziness with 2 episodes of temporary loss of consciousness in a week. Her sodium level was 124 mmol/l and further dropped to 117 mmol/l. The patient experienced dizziness in the morning, she was started on normal saline initially and prescribed with tolvaptan 15mg OD for 3 days to correct the sodium levels and replaced carbamazepine with amitriptyline 10mg PO daily and gabapentin 100mg OD PO for neuropathic pain.

Her next admission was 4 months prior to this admission with the complaints of unconsciousness/syncope associated with palpitations for 30 mins. She presented to her nearby local hospital where MRI brain showed acute infarct in corona radiata region. Then she was admitted to this hospital for the further management. Here in this hospital MRI suggested negative for fresh infarcts, but old infarcts in corona radiata, putamen on the left side, tiny calcified granuloma in right occipital lobe, tiny microbleed in the right temporal lobe was observed. Sodium levels remained 122 mmol/l as before. She was diagnosed with recurrent asymptomatic hyponatremia suspected to be drug induced, and anaemia, CAD – Left carotid bulb 27% stenosis. Started on eslicarbazepine 400mg BD PO for neurological pain and seizure control and corrected

hyponatremia with tolvaptan. Two months ago, of present admission patient presented to a hospital with H/O sudden onset right upper limb & lower limb posturing where she was evaluated and provisionally diagnosed as a seizure, treated with IV levetiracetam and referred to this hospital for further management. MRI was done which showed right medial temporal lobe calcified granuloma and left centrum semiovale chronic infarct. Continued on levetiracetam 500mg PO BD for the seizures and after 15 days patient came back with the complaint of aggravation of trigeminal neuralgia pain for past 2 days which was treated with eslicarbazepine 400mg PO BD and dosulepin (tricyclic anti-depressant) 50mg PO BD. The present

admission due to slip and fall and sustained injury on the right cheek and head. Investigations suggesting recurrent hyponatremia likely eslicarbazepine induced which has been corrected by tolvaptan and patient was recommended to undergo surgery for Trigeminal neuralgia by Radio frequency ablation of nerve she refused to undergo the surgery could have helped her with signs of trigeminal neuralgia to prevent chronic use of carbamazepine which is causing recurrent severe hyponatremia.

she was discharged with the following medications after 3 days of hospital stay. Next review was planned after 60 days post discharge.

Medication	Dose	Frequency	ROA	Duration	Indication
ESLICARBAZEPINE	400 mg	BD	PO	Till review	Trigeminal Neuralgia
DOSULEPIN	50 mg	HS	PO	Till review	Trigeminal Neuralgia
LEVETIRACETAM	500 mg	BD	PO	Till review	Seizures
EZETIMIBE	10 mg	OD	PO	Till review	CAD
LEVOTHYROXINE	37.5 mcg	OD (6AM)	PO	Till review	Hypothyroidism
STROCIT PLUS (CITICOLINE+PIRACETAM)	500mg+800mg	BD	PO	Till review	Neuroprotective
CILINDIPINE	10 mg	OD	PO	Till review	Hypertension
CLONAZEPAM	0.25 mg	OD	PO	Till review	Anxiety
TOLVAPTAN	15 mg	ONCE A WEEK	PO	2 Weeks	Hyponatremia

DISCUSSION

Hyponatremia is a common yet potentially serious electrolyte imbalance, especially in elderly patients with multiple comorbidities and polypharmacy. This case highlights the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges involved in the managing recurrent drug-induced hyponatremia in a 63-year-old woman with a complex medical history that includes trigeminal neuralgia, hypertension, hypothyroidism, seizure disorder, coronary artery disease, and anaemia.

Our patient's recurrent hospital admissions over the past year, each involving varying symptoms from facial pain to transient unconsciousness were eventually linked to a pattern of persistently low serum sodium levels. It is mainly due to the

antiepileptic medications, particularly carbamazepine which is known to cause hyponatremia and later eslicarbazepine which has low potential to cause hyponatremia comparatively but, in this case, even eslicarbazepine has caused hyponatremia. Both the drugs known to cause Syndrome of Inappropriate Antidiuretic Hormone Secretion (SIADH). This mechanism leads to water retention and dilutional hyponatremia, which, if unrecognized or left untreated, can result in neurological symptoms and complications such as seizures and falls.

In her first visit to this hospital, she was prescribed carbamazepine for trigeminal neuralgia, which later caused significant hyponatremia (sodium dropped to as low as 117 mmol/L), leading to dizziness and

syncope. Carbamazepine was then changed to eslicarbazepine, although it is expected to reduce side effects, still has a risk for sodium imbalance, which is evident in this case. The recurring episodes of hyponatremia were corrected with tolvaptan, a vasopressin V2-receptor antagonist that promotes free water excretion without electrolyte loss. The repeated requirement for Tolvaptan, indicates the severity of her hyponatremia. It was used to correct sodium levels, but long-term reliance on this agent is not ideal due to cost, short duration of action, and the risk of overcorrection. So, in order to solve the problem in long term, medical team suggested surgical intervention for trigeminal neuralgia which is Radiofrequency ablation. Post operatively dependence on carbamazepine and eslicarbazepine would greatly reduced, but upon counselling the she has refused to undergo the surgery. What stood out most in this case was the importance of recognizing the medication side-effect profile, especially in elderly patients. The correlation between her antiepileptic regimen and recurrent hyponatremia was not immediately obvious but became clear with repeated admissions and pattern recognition. This also reflects the significance of good follow-up care and patient education regarding symptom awareness and early reporting.

Challenges:

- **Hard to diagnose:** Diagnosing carbamazepine-induced hyponatremia was a challenge since the patient presented with so many overlapping symptoms and multiple health issues.
- **Balancing the multiple therapies:** Managing seizures and trigeminal neuralgia effectively, while minimizing the risk of recurrent hyponatremia, and other cardiovascular diseases was a major clinical challenge.
- **Adverse events:** Patient had multiple admissions for dizziness, fainting, and injury due to severe of electrolyte imbalance caused by medications. Monitoring and minimizing such events need active involvement of clinical pharmacy services and proper patient education.

- **Patient refusal for the surgery:** The patient refused to undergo a surgery for trigeminal neuralgia to prevent chronic use of carbamazepine which is causing recurrent severe hyponatremia.
- **Risk for polypharmacy:** Patient had other comorbidities, for which she had to take multiple drugs, which required careful observation to prevent any drug duplication, drug interactions and additional side effects from occurring.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this case highlights how crucial it is to identify and treat drug-induced hyponatremia, especially in older patients with comorbidities and chronic polypharmacy. This case involved a 63-year-old woman who had been admitted to the hospital several times in the previous year due to recurrent episodes of symptomatic drug-induced hyponatremia brought on by antiepileptic medications such as carbamazepine and eslicarbazepine. Her medical history included trigeminal neuralgia, seizure disorders, and coronary artery disease. She was initially diagnosed with trigeminal neuralgia, which was treated with carbamazepine. However, she experienced severe hyponatremia, for which carbamazepine was stopped and switched to gabapentin. Later, because of the uncontrollable pain from the trigeminal neuralgia, eslicarbazepine was added. Despite the symptoms improvement, the patient continued to experience recurring hyponatremia, disorientation, altered awareness, and a recent subarachnoid haemorrhage as a result of trauma and a fall. Tolvaptan and intravenous fluids were used to repeatedly raise her sodium levels, and the clinical team have tried to find the balance between managing her trigeminal neuralgia and preventing further electrolyte imbalances. The patient refused surgery even though it was suggested that RF (Radio frequency) ablation would permanently relieve her trigeminal neuralgia and allow her to stop using carbamazepine. Later patient was discharged hemodynamically in stable condition requiring medications and patient counselling about monitoring of electrolytes.

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